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IMPROVEMENT OF AIRCRAFT MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR TASKS BASED ON THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13767828>

Abstract: This thesis provides detailed information on aircraft maintenance and repair using information technology. In addition, special attention is paid to the development of models and algorithms for solving these problems.

Keywords: technology, aircraft, aircraft engine, maintenance, repair, model, algorithm, airplane, workshop, management.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, most aviation manufacturing enterprises use a domestic method of organizing the maintenance and repair of aircraft and aircraft engines. This is a waste of time at meetings, conferences, reviews and discussions when making any decisions on the tasks of maintenance and repair of aircraft. Naturally, this is a waste of 20% to 40% of useful time, as a result of which the duration of the maintenance or repair cycle increases and leads to a constant increase in the cost of the MRO service. Domestic and international practice of many aviation enterprises shows that there is an intensive struggle to reduce MRO costs to improve the efficiency of aircraft operation. The main goal of the dissertation research is the activity of the applicant aimed at developing and improving their abilities, increasing the efficiency of using aircraft and ensuring flight safety, significantly related to the state of the functional systems of aircraft, increasing the requirements for safety and regularity of flights, increasing the costs of their maintenance and repair, which requires searching for and implementing new effective methods of technological processes for the maintenance of aircraft equipment. This paper presents information on aircraft maintenance and repair (AMR) issues using information technologies. Particular attention is paid to the development of models and algorithms for solving these problems.

The main requirement for the MAR process as a whole is to ensure the readiness of the aircraft to perform its main functions with the lowest possible

costs. In this regard, this work is relevant for civil aviation enterprises and has practical significance in increasing the competitiveness of domestic enterprises.

Today, more and more airlines are joining the fight to improve their operational efficiency, and they have enormous growth potential in this area. Each airline has production workshops and departments or divisions servicing aircraft of Western or Eastern manufacture.

For example, Uzbekistan Airways Technics LLC is a structural division of Uzbekistan Airways JSC, with extensive experience in the field of MAR of aircraft, engines and components. The modern complex of UAT LLC performs maintenance and repair of aircraft and their components, such as Boeing 737/747/757/767/787, Airbus 300/310/318/319/320/321.

Development of models and algorithms for decision-making in the tasks of aircraft maintenance and repair based on the use of information technologies is one of the initial stages of aircraft maintenance and repair optimization. A necessary condition for organizing the use of information technologies at aviation manufacturing enterprises is the creation of a single information space (complex), with the help of which all automated control systems of an aviation enterprise, as well as departments, workshops and divisions can quickly and promptly exchange information.

One of the most important conditions for the implementation of an automated control system for organizing aircraft maintenance and repair work (digital production) using information technologies (model and algorithm for decision-making) is the functionality that will automatically collect data on the work performed by all production facilities (aircraft, ground equipment, tools, workplaces of enterprise employees, supplies (spare parts and consumables), auxiliary service departments, departments, laboratories, etc.) into a single information space (comprehensive database), for the purpose of operational management of production during aircraft maintenance and repair in an aircraft repair enterprise [1,2]. An example of such functionality is a smart system for monitoring maintenance and repair work, which allows monitoring the work of production personnel in real time, classifying and analyzing their work, conducting operational dispatching of workshop and service departments, transmitting information to the information space (comprehensive database), issuing reporting information, interacting with production planning and management systems. First of all, the appropriate automation of processes should be carried out in this direction. For integrated management of maintenance, repair work, costs, inventory control and purchase of spare parts, the following

software products have been created and developed: AMOS, HubEx, RealMaint and others.

Therefore, aircraft repair enterprises need to create low-cost products, which requires increasingly rapid development and implementation of various methods, devices and systems, while the intellectual level of software is of great importance. At the same time, one of the main requirements for software is the ability to quickly and in real time evaluate output data and obtain analytical results. In this regard, it is necessary to develop models and algorithms for maintenance and repair and the use of information technology.

The use of such software in aircraft maintenance and repair can have the following beneficial effects:

- 1. Improved safety;*
- 2. Reduced workload on personnel;*
- 3. Increased efficiency;*
- 4. Process optimization;*
- 5. Improved service quality.*

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